

Enabling production re-configurability through Digital Twins: A case study approach.*

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Abstract

This paper explores the integration of Digital Twins and smart services within Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems to enhance adaptability, efficiency, and decision-making in modular production environments. Through four industrial case studies, we derive business and system requirements, leading to the development of a conceptual architecture that supports real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimization. The results demonstrate significant improvements in lead time, production efficiency, and operational costs, while also identifying challenges such as DT configuration complexity and interoperability issues. The proposed conceptual architecture introduces a scalable, microservices-based approach that enables distributed intelligence, seamless reconfiguration, and enhanced interoperability between production modules, marking a step forward in the evolution of flexible and data-driven manufacturing ecosystems.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems, Business Requirements, User Requirements, System Analysis

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1 Introduction

Modern manufacturing integrates smart factory technologies, creating interconnected, flexible systems capable of autonomous decision-making and adapting to dynamic market demands, driving global innovation and competitiveness [1]. Reconfigurable Manufacturing Systems (RMSs) embody this model, ensuring continuous operations while rapidly adjusting to shifting production needs [2]. Their agility is key to handling product variety and fluctuating demand, with a modular design that enables quick reconfiguration and enhanced system flexibility by focusing on product families rather than individual items.

RMSs have had little industrial adoption, even though they offer a significant value proposition, with several implementations indicating great potential. An important reason for this is the lack of methods to support their actual development, mainly with regards to modularity [3]. Modularity addresses both physical and functional aspect of a module. Existing methods for modularity include Design Structure Matrix and Modular Function Deployment. However, these methods are purely static ones. Recent studies [4] highlight the importance of resolving this “static” consideration in the transition from traditional manufacturing to RMS. That is, enabling the virtual design to evolve in line with reality by incorporating real-time information into the initial model.

Digital Twins (DTs) have recently been proposed to enhance modularity [5]. In reconfigurable environments, where demand fluctuations and flexibility pose challenges, DTs play a crucial role in decision-making. Designing and selecting an RMS configuration is inherently complex [6], as the number of possible setups grows significantly. Additionally, managing unexpected events like machine failures and improving production resilience remain key priorities [7]. DTs enable flexible decision-making, selecting optimal configurations based on real-time, predicted, and historical data. These decisions are typically supported by intelligent services such as optimization [8–10], simulation [9, 11, 12], and self-awareness or predictive maintenance [13]. Intuitively, DTs along with additional sophisticated capabilities of such smart services, could play the role of an enabler or enhancer of RMSs.

This paper presents a comprehensive framework for integrating DTs within RMSs to enhance modularity, flexibility, and efficiency in modern industrial environments. By analyzing four real-world industrial case studies, the research derives business and user requirements, identifies Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and proposes a conceptual architecture that enables scalable, data-driven manufacturing. A key contribution of this work is the introduction of the “Module” concept, which pairs physical production modules with their DT counterparts, facilitating real-time monitoring, self-awareness, predictive maintenance, simulation, and optimization. Unlike existing theoretical DT frameworks, the proposed approach ensures interoperability and seamless system reconfiguration, leveraging a microservices-based architecture for improved scalability and distributed intelligence. Additionally, the study highlights technical and business challenges in DT adoption, including integration complexity, standardization issues, and digital transformation barriers in legacy manufacturing systems. The findings demonstrate significant improvements in lead time, production efficiency, and operational costs, reinforcing the potential of DT-driven RMSs.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant academic literature, while Section 3 presents the case study analysis and outlines the methodology used to extract business requirements. Section 4 details the functional and non-functional user requirements, along with the corresponding domain model. The conceptual architecture of the proposed information system is introduced in Section 5, accompanied by workflow examples from each case study. Section 6 discusses implementation guidelines and examines the impact of the proposed functionalities across the four case studies, highlighting key limitations and identifying avenues for future research. Finally, Section 7 presents the conclusions of this study.

2 Background and literature review

In this section we present a review of the related academic literature with respect to 3 aspects: (a) first we explore the traditional manufacturing systems and their limits, focusing on the need for modular manufacturing and distributed control (Section 2.1), (b) then we examine existing DT technologies for RMSs (Section 2.2) and (c) we list the related KPIs to RMSs (Section 2.3). This approach outlines the shift from traditional production systems to RMSs while highlighting emerging technological requirements. It examines the role of DTs in facilitating this transition and presents the KPIs used for evaluation. Ultimately, this provides a comprehensive overview of the technological and operational requirements of RMSs as documented in existing literature.

2.1 Traditional manufacturing systems vs RMSs

Traditional manufacturing systems served the industry well for decades. However, they are characterized by their limited adaptability and struggle to keep the pace with these changes [14]. RMS emerged a couple of decades ago [15], as a more flexible solution to varying market demands. The original definition [15] is as follows: “RMS is a production system designed to match the dynamic market asking for high-quality products in variable quantities and at a reasonable cost. RMS has a changeable hardware and software structure allowing adjusting production capacity and functionality to combine high throughput rate, flexibility and cellular organisation pattern.” The core characteristics are modularity, integrability, diagnosability, convertibility, customization, and scalability. Hence, these features enable RMS to produce a variety of customized products while maintaining high efficiency and responsiveness to market changes [6, 14, 16].

Indeed, RMSs are designed to be highly adaptable, allowing for rapid reconfiguration to supporting forms of products and mechanized production systems. The six core characteristics of RMSs are [6, 14]:

- i. **Scalability:** The ability to modify production capacity by adding or removing resources and changing system components to meet varying demand.
- ii. **Convertibility:** The ability to transform the functionality of existing systems to fit new production requirements.
- iii. **Diagnosability:** The ability to monitor in real-time the product quality and the rapid identification of defects.

- iv. **Customization:** The ability to limited to a family of parts, enabling efficient production of customized products.
- v. **Modularity:** The ability of classification the functions into units that can be reconfigured to suit different production schemes.
- vi. **Integrability:** The ability of rapid and precise integration of modules through standardized hardware and software interfaces.

On the technological frontier of the RMS concept, a significant development is distributed control. Unlike traditional centralized control systems, distributed control operates across many devices and locations within the manufacturing environment [17, 18]. This approach improves system resilience, scalability, and flexibility, making it suitable for RMS. For instance, in a smart factory context, distributed control allows for analyzing data real-time and decision-making across connected devices and systems [18]. This configuration improves operational efficiency and supports the integration of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Big Data Analytics into the manufacturing process [16].

2.2 DTs and RMSs

The integration of DT technologies into RMSs stands out as a significant advancement in manufacturing [4]. DTs enable the creation of a virtual replica of physical assets, processes, and systems, which can be used for real-time monitoring, analytics, simulation, diagnostics, and optimization [19]. This technology enhances rapid factory transformation through capabilities such as self-layout recognition, rapid workstation reprogramming, and configurable software for shop-floor monitoring [18]. The application of DT technologies in RMS includes frameworks and methodologies that apply IoT, AI, and Big Data Analytics to achieve the optimal connection between the physical and digital worlds. Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of DTs in enhancing the operational efficiency and flexibility of RMS, building the path for more innovative and resistant manufacturing solutions [20, 21].

The implementation of DTs in RMSs leverages several key technologies and methodologies. DTs integrated into RMS use multiple technologies and techniques, such as Modular Design, which ensures the RMS can be easily reconfigured at both the software and hardware levels to meet varying production needs through quick addition, removal, or rearrangement of components [20]. Real-time Data Integration utilizes sensors or IoT to capture and analyze system information in real-time, providing a continuous data flow that can simulate and predict system behavior under different real-world conditions [4]. Optimization Algorithms, such as the Particle Swarm Optimization, are employed to enhance system performance, particularly in the organization and control of manufacturing cells [4]. Lastly, Cyber-Physical Systems integration connects the mechanical and electronic aspects of a manufacturing system, increasing its flexibility and responsiveness [20].

Existing frameworks for DTs in RMS help in acquiring more flexibility, adaptability, and efficiency through the improved computational Pipelines, Multi-Physics Solvers, and Real-Time Data Analytics [22]. There are various attempts to support the integration of DT in RMS and many frameworks and models have been proposed.

An early approach [4] introduces a five-dimensional DT modeling approach for manufacturing systems. This approach not only enables the mapping between physical and virtual twins but also enhances reconfigurability through expandable model structures and optimized algorithms. The five dimensions of this plan include geometry, physics, capability, behavior, and rules [4]. Similarly is highlighted the necessity of a compact size DT model to accommodate several information technologies like IoT, cloud computing, AI and Big Data Analytics [20]. This structure has scope to support the evaluation and optimization of RMS by affording real-time data and enabling rapid actions to production requirements and market changes [20, 23].

The benefits of DTs when applied in RMSs are various and focus on several aspects. First, DTs enhance flexibility and adaptability in RMSs by allowing them to adjust to new product designs and production volumes, thus reducing downtime and boosting efficiency [4, 24]. They also improve decision-making by providing valuable data insights that enable proactive maintenance and optimization of production processes [4]. Second, DTs enable the use of smart services for decision support, such as simulation where different production configurations can be tested before put to practice [25]. Additionally, DT helps reduce costs through virtual testing and optimization, minimizing the expenses related to the physical reconfiguration of production modules [20]. Moreover, DT-driven RMS can optimize production schedules, reduce waste, and enhance overall productivity through continuous monitoring and process adjustments [22].

2.3 KPI literature review

In the context of Industry 4.0, various parameters have been proposed to support manufacturing companies in measuring economic, environmental, and social parameters across the value chain and lifecycle [26]. Despite this, companies struggle to understand and select the appropriate indicators to measure, monitor, and improve performance [27]. According to an early study [28], measuring KPIs effectively, such as cost, financial, quality, time, flexibility, delivery reliability, safety, customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, and social performance indicators, relates to the company's organisational performance. An additional study [29] also supports the idea that manufacturing companies should have a holistic approach to the KPIs, ensuring compatibility across all supply chains and enhancing cross-company optimization. To this end, examining KPIs relevant to a more significant number of companies is crucial. Also, despite the huge amount of available KPIs, measuring and reporting only what matters could be essential for companies [30].

In particular, regarding RMS, various KPIs should be accessed, such as cost, utilization, quality, lead time, ramp-up time, and reconfiguration time [31]. In the RMS context, manufacturing companies should combine key business factors and indicators to control the system [32]. One of the most prominent indicators to assess an RMS performance is reconfiguration and ramp-up time [31, 33]. Reconfiguration time is the duration of modifying a manufacturing system to produce a different product or adapt to a new process. In contrast, ramp-up time is about to reach production capacity after these modifications. Additionally, two studies [34, 35] propose a set of

indicators to measure the key characteristics of reconfigurability, such as integrability, convertibility and customization. Overall, Table 1 summarizes the results of the literature review. The main identified KPIs relevant to the scope of our study are presented in the "KPIs" column, while the corresponding academic sources are listed in the "Literature" column. A brief description of each KPI and their importance is also provided in the "Details" column.

Table 1: Literature-related KPIs

KPI	Details	Literature
Supply Chain Costs	The total costs involved in managing the supply chain, including logistics, warehousing, and transportation. Importance: Vital for optimizing supply chain operations and reducing related costs.	[36–39]
Lead Time	The time taken from receiving an order to delivering the product to the customer. Importance: Impacts customer satisfaction and inventory management.	[26, 31, 36, 40, 41]
Manufact. Costs	The total costs involved in producing goods, including materials, labour, energy and overhead. Importance: Directly impacts product pricing and profitability.	[42–44]
Productivity	Measures output relative to input in the production process. Importance: Essential for assessing and optimizing resource utilization and efficiency.	[31, 45–47]
Production Time	The time taken from starting to completing the production of a unit. Importance: Crucial for managing production schedules and ensuring timely delivery.	[48–50]
Production Capacity	The total production capability of a manufacturing process or facility, often compared to its actual output. Importance: Vital for understanding the utilization of production resources and identifying underused capacity or overloads.	[31, 45]
Assembly Stability	It measures the uniformity of the production rate in the assembly process over time. Importance: Ensuring consistent production pacing and timely product delivery.	[51]
Due Date Performance	This could be interpreted as a measure of the system's ability to meet delivery deadlines. Importance: This is a crucial aspect of performance in any manufacturing system.	[52]

KPI	Details	Literature
Reconfig. Time	The time it takes to reconfigure the manufacturing system. Importance: A measure of how quickly the system can adapt to new requirements.	[52, 53]
Ramp-up Time	The period required to reach full production capacity after changes in the production line. Importance: It is essential for RMS to quickly adapt and meet market demands.	[31, 33]
Reconfig. Characteristics	Indicators that measure the critical characteristics of reconfigurability, such as integrability, convertibility and customization Importance: Measure the reconfiguration potential and ease of a system.	[34, 35]
Energy Consumption	Measures the amount of energy consumed in the manufacturing process. Importance: Facilitating the identification of opportunities to reduce energy consumption and costs.	[41, 54–58]
Emissions	Monitors the release of pollutants into the air during production. Importance: Ensuring compliance with air quality standards and reduces environmental impact.	[40, 59–61]

2.4 Insights on RMS and DTs

Interestingly, the majority of papers focusing on this subject tend to follow static modularity frameworks, while fewer adopt a more dynamic, even real-time system reconfiguration approach. While prior research has focused on DTs for basic monitoring, simulation, and optimization, these approaches often lack adaptability. Intuitively, there seems to be a gap for a fully integrated DT system that connects business requirements with functional DT capabilities, enabling real-time decision-making and automation. The latter can be achieved through enabling smart services such as, self-awareness, predictive maintenance, sustainability analytics, simulation and optimization, leading to more responsive and efficient manufacturing operations compared to traditional RMS.

Unlike previous works that primarily discuss theoretical DT frameworks or limited lab-based implementations, this study employs a case study-driven approach to derive concrete business, user, and functional requirements. The incorporation of four real-world industrial applications demonstrates the tangible impact of DT-enabled reconfiguration in manufacturing. By integrating DTs with modular production environments, the paper goes beyond isolated factory operations and introduces interoperable production modules that function across multiple companies. Notably, two case studies explore supply chain collaboration, highlighting the potential of DT-enhanced production modules to streamline logistics, warehouse management, and production scheduling in a distributed manufacturing ecosystem.

3 Case study analysis

In this section we present our case study approach (Section 3.1), provide the details of the case studies and summarize the corresponding requirements in terms of KPIs (Section 3.2). In Section 3.3 these KPIs are validated via mapping them on the literature KPIs from the previous section.

The presented case studies are drawn from five industrial organizations that participate in an ongoing EU research project focusing on RMSs via DTs. These organizations aim to leverage digital solutions to address manufacturing challenges, enhance KPIs, and shape future systems for improved operational support. This collaboration has provided valuable insights into the practical challenges and aspirations of implementing RMS and DTs in real-world settings.

These case studies were carefully chosen based on several key factors that highlight both their differences and complementarities. While each case study represents a distinct manufacturing domain, they collectively cover a wide spectrum of industrial challenges, ensuring a diverse and comprehensive analysis. Each industry operates under its own unique set of operational KPIs, emphasizing different performance objectives that need to be met. Furthermore, the case studies exhibit varying requirements for system reconfiguration, ranging from single-module adjustments to more complex multi-module transformations, which adds depth to the study of modularity and flexibility.

Another critical aspect of differentiation among these case studies is their technological needs concerning self-awareness, predictive maintenance, optimization, and simulation. While some cases require enhanced monitoring and intelligent decision-making capabilities, others demand advanced predictive analytics and simulation tools to optimize performance and adaptability. Additionally, two of the case studies function independently, focusing on internal process improvements, while the remaining two operate within a collaborative framework, demonstrating the necessity of interoperability between production systems.

Moreover, the selected case studies differ in their expectations regarding system enhancements. Specifically, two of them require a comprehensive reconfiguration framework integrated with intelligent services, such as simulation and optimization, to support the development of entirely new production modules. In contrast, the remaining case studies aim to enhance the efficiency and adaptability of existing production modules rather than create new ones from scratch. This distinction allows for a thorough evaluation of how DTs and smart manufacturing technologies can be leveraged for both incremental improvements and large-scale transformations.

Ultimately, these variations contribute to the formulation of a unified system capable of accommodating a broad range of requirements related to reconfigurability, modularity, and intelligence. By addressing the diverse needs of different manufacturing setups, this study ensures the development of a flexible and scalable framework that can be adapted to various industrial scenarios. The resulting system will not only facilitate enhanced decision-making and automation but also offer a robust foundation for future advancements in modular manufacturing and intelligent production ecosystems.

3.1 Case study approach

This section outlines the versatile approach adopted, as illustrated in Figure 1, underscoring the methodologies employed to capture a deep understanding of user needs across four case studies. Interaction between manufacturers was necessary only for the third and fourth case studies, involving the collaboration between two industrial partners from similar sectors.

Fig. 1 Case study analysis process

The elicitation process began with understanding the application domain and identifying key stakeholders to outline user needs and additional requirements. A streamlined approach utilizing a comprehensive questionnaire facilitated in-depth insights, encouraging internal discussions within each organization/case study. Follow-up interviews and dedicated meetings were essential in aligning visions and expectations.

Then, we employed semi-structured interviews with key representatives from each industrial site. This included site directors and technology experts aiming at understanding current practices, identifying areas for improvement, and exploring the

integration of technologies for modular manufacturing. This process was supported by a structured questionnaire divided into four parts:

- **(A) Overview of Organization, Products, and Processes (7 questions):** This part seeks comprehensive descriptions of the organization’s product lines, manufacturing processes, and key stakeholders involved.
- **(B) Current Operational Situation (5 questions):** Requests in-depth details on the existing operational conditions, challenges faced in current manufacturing setups, and areas requiring improvement.
- **(C) Future Operational Goals (8 questions):** Aims to gather insights on the desired state of operations, improvements sought, and specific objectives related to modular manufacturing enhancements.
- **(D) ICT Infrastructure and Data Management (18 questions):** Solicits detailed information on the current state of ICT infrastructure, data access, and availability, focusing on how technology supports manufacturing processes and the potential for integration with new modular manufacturing solutions.

The validation of identified use cases involved thorough review and feedback from industrial stakeholders and requirements as found in the literature. The primary goal with industrial pilots was to confirm that use cases accurately reflected user requirements and needs. This iterative process of review, analysis, adjustments, and validation was conducted offline, through shared documents for comments, and via direct communications with the involved stakeholders.

The selection of specific KPIs was guided by the involved organizations in each case study, ensuring alignment with their current operational challenges and future goals in the context of modular manufacturing. Each organization provided insights into their existing production systems, identifying bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and reconfiguration needs that hinder adaptability and scalability. These case studies span various industrial domains, each with distinct yet complementary requirements for flexibility, automation, and optimization. The selected KPIs reflect the organizations’ pain areas, such as reducing production lead times, enhancing process efficiency. Additionally, their future operational goals focus on improving sustainability, integrating predictive maintenance, and enhancing self-aware production modules that can dynamically adjust to changing demands.

3.2 Case study descriptions

In this section we describe in detail the requirements and objectives (in terms of KPIs) of each case study. The latter are numbered and identified by using the CS number and the KPI number, e.g., KPI_{x.y} with x being the CS number and y the KPI number.

3.2.1 CS1: Manufacturer of industrial robotic equipment

This case study involves a leading manufacturer specializing in custom robotic equipment for diverse industrial sectors. It focuses on the development of innovative production modules equipped with robotic systems tailored for specific manufacturing tasks, such as precision welding or material handling. These modules are designed to incorporate advanced sustainability and optimization features, enabling precise

calculations of energy consumption and carbon emissions for various manufacturing activities. The goal is to refine robotic operations for greater efficiency, reducing both energy use and environmental impact. Additionally, the company supports the enhancement of modular product design processes, covering all aspects from tool selection and robotic simulation to virtual commissioning and rigorous testing before deployment in manufacturing environments.

To achieve this the organization wishes to incorporate sustainability analytics and Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) to guide its operations. It will critically examine different robot design setups, aiming to identify those that best balance efficiency and environmental impact. The process involves designing and simulating robot operations for specific manufacturing tasks, with focus on assessing how different design setups affect performance and sustainability. Optimizing robot movements for a given design setup is key, ensuring tasks are performed not only efficiently but also in a proper manner that aligns with sustainability criteria. This approach is supplemented by virtual commissioning and physical testing of robots, ensuring that each robotic system meets operational and environmental standards before being deployed in manufacturing environments.

The case study sets forth ambitious KPIs to enhance sustainability and efficiency in manufacturing processes through innovative design and robotic system optimization:

- **KPI1.1:** Reduction of energy consumption over the duration of the production process by 10% via optimizing the design process and the robotic system operations;
- **KPI1.2:** Reduction of carbon emissions over the duration of the production process by 5% at minimum (direct relation to energy consumption) via optimizing the design process and the robotic system operations;
- **KPI1.3:** Design of new production modules with sustainability capabilities;
- **KPI1.4:** Incorporation of detailed energy and sustainability parameters in the environmental impact assessment (i.e., energy, greenhouse gas emissions, and heat produced).

3.2.2 CS2: Manufacturer of gearmotors

The second case study focuses on a transformation within a manufacturing company, shifting from a traditional, highly automated production system to a more flexible, modular RMS for assembling gearmotors. This is driven by the need for extreme customization to meet the specific customer requirements, leading to a wide variety of products and necessitating small-sized or single-lot production batches. The company is developing its first modular assembly plant to streamline this process, aiming to incorporate advanced reconfiguration and simulation capabilities. Additionally, the project seeks to enhance the production modules with self-awareness and optimization features for improved efficiency and predictive maintenance.

To achieve the transformation the organization wishes to implement several key measures. Initially, it seeks to monitor the current capacity of production cells to efficiently manage resources. This involves comparing performance across identical cells to identify discrepancies and enhance uniformity. To prevent failures, the system will

alert about production modules at risk, integrating self-awareness for proactive management. Predictive maintenance notifications will further streamline care, ensuring modules are serviced before issues arise. Optimizing the production schedule is crucial, incorporating predictive maintenance insights and adjusting production routing to meet custom requirements. This extends to re-optimizing schedules or rerouting production as new needs emerge, ensuring flexibility and responsiveness. Additionally, the company aims to design or reconfigure production steps, cells, and modules, balancing resources for various process setups and performing simulations to validate their efficiency against specific schedules or product specifications. Finally, the ability to declare process drifts, like delays or bottlenecks, ensures timely intervention, maintaining operational fluidity.

The following KPIs are established to measure and drive improvements in the manufacturing processes:

- **KPI2.1:** Reduction of global lead-time by 80%, which is the time needed to complete each customer order from the entry to the exit of the production process;
- **KPI2.2:** Increase of global productivity by 33%, which is the number of gearmotors assembled per operator per shift;
- **KPI2.3:** Increase of global output by ± 10 gearmotors per hour, which is the output for the global production process;
- **KPI2.4:** Increase of global capacity by 45% which is the sum of capacity per production step, through investment in new cells or modifying existing cells;
- **KPI2.5:** Reduction of production time by 33%, which is the time that the equipment is being used;
- **KPI2.6:** Reduction of production area per gearmotor per day by 33%, which is the daily productivity area required to set up the production line;
- **KPI2.7:** Increase of automatic scheduling rate by 25%, which is the automatically scheduled orders.

3.2.3 CS3: Manufacturer in the polymer material sector

This case study involves a company specializing in the design and production of expanded polypropylene components, renowned for its commitment to product and process quality. Currently, the organization focuses on the development for its customers of a reconfigurable “smart” Kit-Holder (KH) aimed at enhancing the efficiency of handling and transportation of semi-finished goods within automotive manufacturing. This modular solution is designed to quickly adapt to varying production demands, emphasizing the improvement of operational efficiency and quality through advanced monitoring capabilities. To do so, this KH may include within its frame different blocks that may be used to hold any type of component or semi-finished product that needs to be transported to production. Both the frame and the blocks is custom-designed, hence the corresponding KH may be used for any combination of blocks and may be quickly and modularly adapted to fit any changes in production.

The development of the reconfigurable “smart” KH is crucial not only for its direct application but also as it will be provided to enhance the operational efficiency in the fourth case study’s warehousing system.

To achieve this the organization wishes to deploy advanced monitoring for production machinery, ensuring optimal operation in creating the KH components. By integrating self-awareness notifications, they aim to stay ahead of potential disruptions, ensuring continuous production flow. Tracking the inbound and outbound logistics of each KH order will enhance supply chain transparency, while simulating new material handling and intra-logistics systems will assess potential performance improvements. Finally, analyzing usage data of the KH will inform design refinements, supporting continuous improvement in both product and process efficiency.

The organization aims to improve the following KPIs:

- **KPI3.1:** Increase of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) for KH production machines by 6%;
- **KPI3.2:** Reduction of the NVAA manual operations by 100%;
- **KPI3.3:** Design and development of a new KH.

3.2.4 CS4: Automotive manufacturer

The last case study features a leading automotive Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) with global operations. This company showcases expertise in automotive engineering, manufacturing, advanced materials, ICT, and electronics. It boasts state-of-the-art laboratories and comprehensive testing facilities, including advanced engine and vehicle testing, Electro Magnetic Compatibility (EMC) chambers, and a virtual reality driving simulator, highlighting its innovation and excellence in the automotive industry. The organization explores the deployment of a “smart” KH in an automated warehousing system aimed at streamlining warehousing and production operations. Enhancing communication with Kitting Robot Systems (KRSs) for precise picking tasks, this setup aims to refine the production workflow, cutting down cycle times and resolving manufacturing bottlenecks. This effort is further advanced by integrating the “smart” KH developed in the preceding case study, illustrating a strategic link between stages of the supply chain to boost overall productivity and efficiency.

To achieve this the organization wishes to systematically manage the content and configuration of each “smart” KH, ensuring that all specifications are up-to-date and meet quality standards. Key to this process is the capability to receive timely notifications about any KHs that fall short of quality expectations. Monitoring the timely delivery of KHs from the KRSs to the production line is crucial for maintaining a smooth workflow. The organization seeks to automate the KRSs’ ability to identify the contents of each KH, optimizing the picking process by determining which parts are needed next. Furthermore, there’s a focus on refining the KRS picking sequence for each KH, aiming for optimal efficiency in preparation for delivery. Lastly, evaluating various picking sequences against different KRS configurations will enable the organization to pinpoint the most effective strategies for enhancing productivity and reducing cycle times in the warehousing and assembly processes.

Through these enhancements the organization aims to improve the following KPIs:

- **KPI4.1:** Reduction of KRS reprogramming time by 75%, the whole procedure is modular and assisted by the project DT features;
- **KPI4.2:** Reduction of the average time for KH preparation by 20%, at minimum;

- **KPI4.3:** Reduction of disruptions due to uncertainty of in-plant logistics by 25%, at minimum;
- **KPI4.4:** Increase of OEE for optimized KH preparation operations by 11%, at minimum;
- **KPI4.5:** Reduction of the Non-Value-Added Activities (NVAA) manual operations by 45%.

3.3 Business and literature KPIs

Once all business requirements and the respective KPIs are identified, it is important to validate them against with the respective KPIs as found in the academic literature and reported in Section 2.3. Table 2 shows this mapping; Column “Literature KPI” refers to the respective KPI as found in the literature, while the “Business KPI” refers to the respective KPI(s) as identified in each CS.

Table 2: Mapping of Business to Literature KPIs

Literature KPI	Business KPI	Literature
Supply Chain Costs	KPI3.2, KPI4.5	[36–39]
Lead Time	KPI2.1	[26, 31, 36, 40, 41]
Manufact. Costs	KPI3.2, KPI4.5	[42–44]
Productivity	KPI2.2, KPI2.3, KPI2.6	[31, 45–47]
Production Time	KPI2.5, KPI4.2	[48–50]
Production Capacity	KPI2.4	[31, 45]
Assembly Stability	KPI4.3	[51]
Due Date Performance	KPI3.1, KPI4.4	[52]
Reconfig. Time	KPI4.1	[52, 53]
Ramp-up Time	KPI2.7, KPI4.1	[31, 33]
Reconfig. Characteristics	KPI1.3, KPI1.4, KPI2.7, KPI3.3, KPI4.1	[34, 35]
Energy Consumption	KPI1.1	[41, 54–58]
Emissions	KPI1.2	[40, 59–61]

4 Requirements analysis

4.1 Main concepts

As discussed in the previous section, the case studies are quite complementary in the issues that they examine. Therefore, we adopt a common perspective to handle them, one that is based on our view on contemporary production modules, what we call the Module, that is the combination of a production module with its DT.

A production module is an asset that carries out specific manufacturing tasks or processes and can be integrated or rearranged with other production modules to create a flexible, modular, and reconfigurable production environment. It can be a physical asset (e.g., a machine, a robot, etc.) or a logical asset (e.g., a group of machines, a production line, etc.); the latter implies that a production module may itself be

composed of other production modules. Furthermore, within the production process, some production modules precede others to complete a set of tasks. Thus, there is a hierarchy and precedence of production modules that comprise the production setting as a whole, hereafter denoted as the production schema. Figure 2 depicts an example of

Fig. 2 Production Schema Example

a production schema illustrating the hierarchy and precedence relationships between production modules. Hence, in this context, a production schema is a model of a production activity. This can be either in actual mode, i.e., the one that is currently used in production, or in design mode, where anyone can design a new production module or schema and experiment on new (re-)configurations to evaluate their impact on production.

The second part of the Module, i.e., the DT, is a virtual replica of a production module, integrating real-time data from sensors to monitor, predict, simulate, or optimize its performance, thus enabling better decision-making and improved efficiency [62]. DTs have been recently proposed to support modularity [5]. Hence, the DT becomes an enabler for new capabilities that a Module could have. That is, each production module is augmented by a DT that may offer a plethora of additional distributed intelligence capabilities, including self awareness, optimization, (co-)simulation, predictive maintenance, and analytics on the operations of the production module. The Module incorporates the flexibility and modularity that a production module can have within a production process, along with the new distributed capabilities that are fostered by its DT. In this regard, we employ a new generation of production modules that are fully integrated and enhanced by their DT. In addition,

when using the Module concept in a modular production environment, it becomes easier to reconfigure and design the performance of a production system, either in actual or design mode.

Most importantly, all Modules should be able to be managed, exchange data, and collaborate in a seamless manner through a reconfigurable digital environment. Hereafter, we denote this environment as the System. This will provide all functionalities that enable the (re-)configuration of Modules and their new capabilities, along with the design of new Modules. This way, users of the System will be able to re-configure, monitor, simulate, optimize, get notified about events in the production process, and design the production schemas that suit their needs, offering enhanced modularity and reconfigurability [14], while also enabling optimized operations for the corresponding RMS.

4.2 Functional and non-functional requirements

In this section we present the functional and non-functional requirements of the proposed System. We present the functional requirements in the form of the Unified Modelling Language (UML) Use Case (UC) diagrams. These UCs along with the non-functional requirements are a distillation of the business requirements obtained by industrial users and stakeholders as described in Section 3.2. We aim to give an abstract view of the functional requirements, grouping them into two categories, i.e., case study agnostic and specific. The first includes functional requirements that apply to all case studies and are prerequisites (i.e., in the form of set-up or re-configuration actions) for the proper System function, while the latter refers to functional requirements that are tailored to each case study need.

First we start with the case study agnostic requirements of the System, focusing on the management and configuration aspects. Following this, we dive into the specific requirements, detailing the unique capabilities associated with each case study. Last, we describe the non-functional requirements.

4.2.1 Case-study-agnostic requirements

Figure 3 demonstrates the case study agnostic UCs, while Table 3 provides a short description of the UCs. These are core to setting up or reconfiguring the System according to the needs of an industrial site.

Table 3: Description of case study agnostic UCs

Use Case	Description
Configure User Account	Enables super users to manage accounts, assign roles, ensure security, and allow users to update their details.
Configure System	Enables super users to set up, update, or remove production schemas, integrating DTs and custom capabilities to align operational and design environments with production needs.

Use Case	Description
Configure Event	Allows super-users to manage custom events, ensuring timely notifications and responses for smooth production operations.

4.2.2 Case-study-specific requirements

In the following UML use case diagrams, the **Use Capability** UC functions as an abstraction, representing the generic ability of the User to utilize various functionalities within the system. The “extend” relationship demonstrates that these specific capabilities are specialized versions of the more general Use Capability function. This structure enables an organized modeling of the system’s functionalities, with the “User” type serving as a generic object that abstracts the various roles involved. This abstraction is useful for representing related functionalities across different types of users, offering an overall view of how the system enables different tasks.

CS1: Manufacturer of industrial robotic equipment. Figure 4 demonstrates the specific UCs to CS1, while Table 4 provides a short description of each UC. The user types that share this functionality are Robot Simulation Users, Process Engineers, Robot Programmers, Virtual Commissioning Engineers, and Plant Operators. To abstract these different types and better demonstrate the related functionality we employed the generic type “User”.

Table 4: Description of CS1 UCs

Use Case	Description
Optimize Robot Movements	Enhances robot efficiency and sustainability by allowing programmers to optimize movements based on operational and sustainability criteria.
Perform Virtual Commissioning	Allows engineers to simulate and assess the sustainability and performance of robot designs, minimizing risks and optimizing production before implementation.
Simulate Robot Operations	Allows engineers to test different robot designs, ensuring optimal performance and task efficiency.
Analyze Sustainability Metrics	Defines methods to assess energy use, emissions, and LCA, helping engineers optimize robot design sustainability.
Monitor Physical Robot Tasks	Provides real-time tracking of robot performance, ensuring smooth operation, issue detection, and production efficiency.
Evaluate Physical Robot Performance	Tests robots in real conditions to ensure they meet production and sustainability criteria.

CS2: Manufacturer of gearmotors. Figure 5 shows the required UCs, while Table 5 provides the description of each UC. The involved user types include Production Scheduling Team Members, Innovation Engineers, Shop-Floor Managers,

Fig. 3 Case Study Agnostic Requirements

Fig. 4 Specific Requirements of CS1

Production Technician, Maintenance Engineers, and Operators. As previously, the “User” is employed for abstraction.

Fig. 5 Specific Requirements of CS2

Table 5: Description of CS2 UCs

Use Case	Description
Receive Self-Awareness Notifications	Alerts users to potential production module failures, enabling proactive issue resolution and technician allocation.
Perform Predictive Maintenance	Provides maintenance schedules and recommendations to ensure optimal production module operation and efficiency.
Optimize Production Schedule	Enhances scheduling by integrating predictive maintenance and constraints, enabling efficient planning, adaptation, and re-optimization.
Evaluate Production Performance	Compares production schedules and cell performance using KPIs to optimize processes and identify improvements.
Monitor Production Process	Provides real-time visibility, allowing users to track capacity, identify bottlenecks, and ensure smooth operations.
Monitor Production Process	Provides real-time visibility, allowing users to track capacity, identify bottlenecks, and ensure smooth operations.

Use Case	Description
Simulate Production Steps	Enables users to test reconfigured setups, comparing performance to select the most effective configuration.
Report Production Status	Allows operators to update working status and report issues, ensuring timely responses for smooth operations.

CS3: Manufacturer in the polymer material sector. Figure 6 shows the required UCs for CS3, while Table 6 provides the description of each UC. The involved user types include Production Managers, Logistics Managers, Plant/Automation Managers, and Design Experts. The term "User" in the diagram abstracts all these roles.

Fig. 6 Specific Requirements of CS3

Table 6: Description of CS3 UCs

Use Case	Description
Receive Self-Awareness Notifications	Alerts the Production Scheduler to KH quality issues, enabling timely order adjustments.
Monitor Production Status	Allows a Production Manager to track machine performance in real-time, ensuring smooth operations and prompt issue resolution.

Use Case	Description
Track Logistic Operations	Allows a Logistic Manager to monitor KH logistics, identifying delays and optimizing delivery for timely, quality transportation.
Simulate Logistics Systems	Allows managers to test new logistics systems, assessing their impact to support informed implementation decisions.
Configure Production Schemas	Allows a Design Expert to manage schemas, optimizing KH quality and functionality based on usage data.

CS4: Automotive manufacturer. Figure 7 shows the required UCs for CS4, while Table 7 provides the description of each UC. The involved user types include Production Managers and Logistics Managers. As previously, the "User" role abstracts these two categories of users.

Table 7: Description of CS4 UCs

Use Case	Description
Receive Self-Awareness Notifications	alerts the Production Manager to KH quality issues, enabling timely action to maintain production standards.
Configure KH Content	Allows a Production Manager to set up and manage KH content, ensuring alignment with operational needs.
Monitor KH Delivery	Allows managers to track KH deliveries, prioritize kitting sequences, and address potential delays for smooth operations.
Automate Module-to-Module Communication	Enables automatic KH content reading and part tracking, ensuring efficient and accurate picking.
Optimize Picking Sequence	Optimizes KRS picking for KHs, ensuring efficiency and accuracy in delivery preparation.
Evaluate Picking Performance	Assesses KRS picking sequences to help the Production Manager ensure optimal efficiency and performance.

4.2.3 Non-functional requirements

Regarding non-functional requirements as elicited by the case studies, the system is expected to tackle a large volume of data. Security issues are of vast importance considering the provided control functionalities. System access is granted through an authentication process. Unauthorized data export is restricted. The System should also be hardware/operating system agnostic. Vertical and horizontal scalability is obligatory. System access is required on a 24/7 basis with almost 100% dependability. The system should be simple to use. For routine operations, user documentation should not be required. All System capabilities should be accessible, with easy navigation

Fig. 7 Specific Requirements of CS4

through all features. Last, individual parts should be able to communicate with one another and utilize the information they share in real-time.

4.3 Data requirements

Figure 8 provides a domain model, i.e., a depiction of the correlations between the core concepts that the System should incorporate. This domain model is based merely on the user perspective; thus, it does not imply or impose any specification for the technical implementation of the System.

The central point of this domain model, as seen from the user perspective, is the Module. Each Module consists of many Modules, thus, this model can support the required hierarchy of production modules. In addition, each Module may be preceded by several Modules in the manufacturing process. Also, each Module is supported by many Capabilities, i.e., business logic that can be implemented, such as sustainability analytics, self-awareness, predictive maintenance, simulation, optimization, Virtual Commissioning, etc. These capabilities can be executed multiple times based on pre-defined input and generate the required output. The Users of the System, based on their User Role, have different access rights to the Modules. In addition, Events, either Custom Events or System Events, that occur in the production environment generate Notifications for a set of specific Users. For completeness, we enclose the definition of each concept below.

- **User:** An end user who uses the System.
- **UserRole:** A predefined category that can be assigned to users on the basis of their job title. Different UserRoles can have different access rights and views of the System.

Fig. 8 Domain Model

- **Module:** A production module accompanied by its DT. The first recursive relationship describes the hierarchy that may occur between Modules, while the second describes the precedence from one Module to another.
- **ProductionSchema:** The setup of the production activity, either in actual or design mode. It consists of multiple Modules.
- **Capability:** Refers to additional business logic that a DT can provide, such as optimization, simulation, analytics, co-optimization, and co-simulation. These capabilities are represented either as executables or algorithms that implement a business logic and can be executed many times to process different input data and provide the respective output.
- **Event:** The description of an incident that takes place in the framework of the System. This includes production process (i.e., CustomEvent) or System events (i.e., SystemEvent).
- **SystemEvent:** An Event that describes System incidents, such as System errors, the termination of a Capability execution, etc.

- **CustomEvent**: An Event that is tailor-made to the user needs imposed by the production environment.
- **Notification**: An alert/indication that an Event took place at a specific time.

5 System conceptual architecture and workflow

In this Section we present the conceptual architecture of the proposed System along with examples its use through workflow diagrams.

5.1 Conceptual architecture

Figure 9 shows the conceptual architecture of the proposed System. It includes two pillars, Pillar 1 and 2 which encompass multiple components functioning as microservices. Notably, DTs of production modules are also regarded as microservices, which are able to work in a distributed manner.

Fig. 9 System conceptual architecture

Pillar 1 offers a novel modular manufacturing environment, where Distributive Control is implemented via interoperable DTs that incorporate control functionalities,

local intelligence and decision support mechanisms, while enabling them to access information thus becoming self-aware and capable to coordinate with other modules via an Interoperability Framework and based on industrial standards to optimize their operations.

The Interoperability Framework & Standards entity is the connection between the System and the manufacturing domain, i.e., production modules as well as information and manufacturing systems. Its basis is the interoperability offered by open interfaces based on industrial standards with the physical or digital assets of a manufacturing process. Furthermore, it enables distributed coordination of modules, incorporating mappings of standardised module interfaces to proprietary ones. In more detail, the Module-to-Module Interface enables direct communication from one module to another (even between modules with proprietary interfaces), thus supporting distributed collaboration. The Interoperability Implementation component includes the implementation of interfaces for integrating modules, as well as enterprise and manufacturing information systems. The Interfaces & Standards Repository component is a repository for interfaces and standards utilized for all communication either internally or externally. More details on the suggested communication protocols and standards is provided in Section 6.1.

The Distributed Control via DTs entity materializes distributed control for production modules. Recall from Sections 4.1 and 4.3 that the Module is a manufacturing element (with its control system) and its DT. Using proper interfaces, the DT enables utilizing the module’s embedded control functionalities in an interoperable manner, but also augments the module’s capabilities by offering additional distributed intelligence tools including Analytics, Self-Awareness, Simulation and Optimization. Any interaction with other modules and/or manufacturing systems flows through the “Interoperability Framework & Standards” entity based on industrial standards and mappings between them.

Pillar 2 enables high-level decisions for module or production line design and reconfiguration driven by data and decisions also stemming from the module-level. This pillar incorporates production domain knowledge and formulates the production-level decision support framework for modular manufacturing staged on Modularity Support Services that enhance the Collective Intelligence and scalability of the solution and offered via an intuitive and easy-to-use Modular Production Toolkit.

The Modular Production Toolkit entity is the interaction point with the end-user. It enables designing or reconfiguring production at different levels, from single modules to whole modular production lines. Depending on the scope, the Production Design/Reconfiguration component offers functionalities that enable designing a new or reconfiguring an existing module or even introducing, removing or reconfiguring process steps accordingly through a user-friendly interface with editing and designing capabilities. Once such changes are made through the design tools, either on a module or production line level, the end-user can utilize the functionalities of the Evaluation & decision Support component to optimize the production processes and evaluate their performance via appropriate dashboards and reporting functionalities. In addition, the Virtual Commissioning component offers functionalities that enable virtual commissioning and analysis of new production modules to enable production simulation and

support industrial decisions towards their adoption and integration within production processes. Moreover, this entity by utilizing the functionalities of the “Collective Intelligence” component of “Modular Support Services”, it enables optimizing and simulating production processes to assess different production schemas and thus evaluate different scenarios to support the corresponding design/reconfiguration decisions. The “Production Knowledge Base” entity is also required to get or update information related to the actual production schema and the respective domain knowledge.

The Production Knowledge Base entity is the knowledge keeper of the production process. Apart from this, it provides access to System data including, production or analyses data. Its interaction with the rest of the entities is vertical, i.e., all entities, components and modules may consult or update the Production Knowledge Base. In more detail, the Module & Production Schema Repository component is responsible for keeping the current production as well as designed/reconfigured ones (which are under consideration) for querying or editing either in a real or a simulated set-up, to enable assessment of different modular production scenarios. The Data Connection Bridge component handles the connection to all production modules and manufacturing information systems.

The Modularity Support Services entity is the core of the System and is comprised of three sub-entities. The Service Operation sub-entity is responsible for managing the operations and services of the whole System. Its first component, i.e., the Service Catalogue, is a central record of all services, along with a resource catalogue available to any authorized user or service. Moreover, the Service Orchestrator component manages all internal operations. Any service required to be (re-)deployed goes through this component. The Event Management sub-entity manages the internal communication and event handling of the System. Its first component, i.e., the Message Bus, is the main and central communication mechanism for all System components which transfers data in a scalable and asynchronous manner. The second component, i.e., the Event Controller, is responsible to process incoming events and trigger the respective System component. The last involved sub-entity is the Collective Intelligence. This part contains all collective intelligence services, i.e., Co-Simulation, Optimization Predictive Maintenance and Sustainability Analytics. Its components are capable of processing data from multiple modules of the production process. In this way, a simulation, optimization, predictive maintenance, or analytics approach can obtain a global view of the whole production process instead of looking only at individual modules. To support this, existing distributed tools, and systems (e.g., for optimization or simulation) are integrated and utilized via general-purpose adaptors and interfaces. Results from these components may be communicated to the “Modularity Support Toolkit”, thus becoming available to the end-user. Relevant information may also be drilled down to the modules, thus enabling distributed control but with a global view.

All these components comprise a modular architecture that can integrate DTs across different manufacturing domains, providing a structured workflow for DT-enabled production. In addition, the microservices architecture enhances system scalability by allowing individual components to scale independently based on demand, ensuring efficient resource utilization. By distributing workloads across multiple

instances of microservices, the system can dynamically adapt to varying loads, improving performance and fault tolerance. Unlike previous studies that offer fragmented DT frameworks, the proposed architecture ensures interoperability, real-time event handling, and self-awareness alerts. In addition, through its classification of services into 2 sets (i.e., pillars 1 and 2), it covers the needs of managing DTs in the lower levels (i.e., single production module level) or higher levels (i.e., multiple production modules) of the production process. Considering that DT-driven systems can optimize decision-making, modular production, and sustainability, this architectural approach attempts to enhance industrial digital transformation. Ultimately, this work sets a foundation for further research on scalable DT frameworks, real-world deployments, and their impact on manufacturing resilience, sustainability, and cross-company collaboration.

5.2 System workflow

Figure 10 shows the workflow of the System configuration operations. The first step is to configure the Production Modules in the production process. Upon completion, a set of DTs is generated and maintained by the System following a one-to-one relation with the Production Modules. That is, every Production Module gets its DT, transforming it this way into a Module. Next, all necessary capabilities are configured to ensure that the Modules can perform as expected. Within this step capabilities such as Optimization, Simulation, Predictive Maintenance, etc., are configured and attached to each Module. Finally, events are configured to set up notifications and responses for specific situations. These operations of configuring the Production Modules, their capabilities and any related or required notification, is fundamental for the proper use and function of the System. Also, note that this workflow involves the Case-Study-agnostic requirements presented in Section 4.2.1.

Fig. 10 System configuration workflow: Step 1 - Configure Production Modules; Step 2 - Configure Capabilities; Step 3 - Configure Events

Regarding CS1, Figure 11 demonstrates an example of use that is tailored to this case study. In this case, the user wishes to assess and improve the performance of a robot design setup. Note that, this setup has been configured following the CS-agnostic flow in Figure 10. The flow begins with the Robot Simulation User simulating a set of given robot movements. Once ready, the Robot Programmer then optimizes the robot movements and if the optimized movements are not optimal, the workflow loops back to simulating step again. Last, the process concludes with the Virtual Commissioning Engineer assessing the performance of this new robot design setup in the targeted manufacturing process. If the results are not meeting the expected performance standards, the process loops back to the previous step.

Fig. 11 CS1 workflow: Step 1 - Robot Operational Simulation; Step 2 - Robot Movement Optimization; Step 3 - Virtual Commissioning

Regarding CS2, in Figure 12 the flow of use begins with a self-awareness notification, which alerts the user for a potential production failure. Once receiving this notification, the user simulates the production process under the expected conditions to evaluate the impact of the foreseen failure. Based on the simulation results, the final step is to optimize the production processes. This workflow approach ensures that any potential issues are tackled, and production operations are optimized.

Fig. 12 CS2 workflow: Step 1 - Self-Awareness Notification; Step 2 - Simulation Production Process; Step 3 - Optimize Production Processes

Regarding CS3, in Figure 13 the flow of use begins with a self-awareness delay notification related to intra-logistics. This notification alerts the user for a potential delay within the logistics system. Considering that this situation might be frequent, the user is willing to investigate the impact of a new intra-logistics system, which could perform better and, hence, avoid such delays. The user then configures a new intra-logistic system to assess its performance. Finally, the execution of the new configured intra-logistic system is simulated and its performance is assessed.

Fig. 13 CS3 workflow: Step 1 - Self-Awareness Delay Notification Intra Logistics; Step 2 - Configure New Intra Logistic System; Step 3 - Simulate Performance

Last, regarding CS4 in Figure 14 the flow of use begins with the configuration of the picking process set-up. This involves the listing of components to be picked and KHs to be filed with them. Next, the configured set-up is used to simulate robot movements. This simulation helps in assessing the performance of the robot in the picking tasks. Finally, the picking sequence is optimized based on the simulation results. This ensures that the picking process is optimal.

It becomes obvious that all CS-specific workflows involve the use of a capability, such as Optimization, Simulation or Predictive Maintenance, along with a custom

Fig. 14 CS4 workflow: Step 1 - Configure Set-Up; Step 2 - Simulation of Robot Movements; Step 3 - Optimize Picking Sequence

notification tailored to the needs of each Case Study. Most importantly, these capabilities are configured for each CS separately by System Configuration workflow. This, by being case-study-agnostic, covers all 4 CSs and stands out as a prerequisite functionality that makes the System usable for each CS.

6 Implementation guidelines and implications

6.1 Implementation guidelines

Implementing DTs using the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) provides significant benefits through standardization. The AAS ensures a unified digital representation of physical assets, enabling seamless interoperability across Industry 4.0 systems. This standardization simplifies communication between heterogeneous devices, reducing complexity and improving scalability. By adopting a common framework, organizations enhance data exchange and decision-making efficiency. Studies show that AAS-based DTs streamline asset integration and enable advanced functions like predictive maintenance and real-time monitoring, contributing to more adaptive and efficient manufacturing systems.

Given that all components in the conceptual architecture function as microservices, both synchronous and asynchronous communication methods are essential. Synchronous communication via RESTful APIs facilitates real-time interactions, commonly used for database queries and IIoT sensor data retrieval. In addition, asynchronous communication via message brokers (e.g., RabbitMQ, Apache Kafka, MQTT) allows independent message processing, enhancing system resilience and scalability. This approach is particularly valuable in event-driven architectures, where real-time data streaming and distributed microservices require efficient, non-blocking data exchange.

External system integration, such as Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), is critical due to the vital information stored within them. OPC UA enables standardized, secure communication between Operational Technology components like PLCs, SCADA, and sensors, ensuring real-time interoperability across manufacturers. Meanwhile, ERP systems manage production planning, inventory, and supply chains. API-based ERP integration facilitates bidirectional communication with MES, DTs, and IoT platforms, automating workflows and ensuring real-time synchronization between shop-floor operations and enterprise management, fostering Industry 4.0 advancements.

To ensure scalability, security, and user accessibility, the proposed architecture follows a microservices-based approach within an on-premises private cloud infrastructure. This approach allows independent scaling of services based on demand,

optimizing resource utilization without overloading the system. By leveraging containerization and orchestration tools, services can be dynamically managed, ensuring high availability and fault tolerance. Security is reinforced through strict access controls, authentication mechanisms, and encrypted communication channels, preventing unauthorized access to sensitive production data. Additionally, the on-premises deployment, which was requested in all CSs, ensures that data remains within the organization’s controlled environment, minimizing external vulnerabilities. User accessibility is enhanced through role-based access control, allowing authorized personnel to interact with relevant system components based on their responsibilities. The suggested architecture also supports web-based interfaces and API integrations, ensuring seamless access across different devices while maintaining strict compliance with security policies and industry standards.

6.2 Impact evaluation

The evaluation of our approach is conducted based on the reported KPIs in each case study (Section 3.2), measuring the effectiveness of the employed system functionalities. The achieved values provide a comprehensive assessment of the functionalities’ impact on production efficiency, operational improvements, and overall performance. Notably, most KPIs have been successfully met or even exceeded, demonstrating significant advancements across various industrial applications. A few indicators have remained unchanged, suggesting areas where the system maintains stability rather than driving immediate improvements. Additionally, a set of KPIs require further research and development, as ongoing investigations aim to optimize these aspects.

In CS1, the manufacturer of industrial robotic equipment highlights the successful integration of sustainability analytics capabilities (KPI1.4) through the introduction of a new AAS sub-model template. This innovation has enabled the design and development of a new production module (KPI1.3) capable of measuring its environmental impact, marking a significant step towards sustainable manufacturing. By embedding real-time monitoring and analytical capabilities, the system aims to enhance energy efficiency and reduce carbon emissions. However, the actual impact on energy consumption (KPI1.1) and emissions reduction (KPI1.2) remains under investigation, as extensive testing is required to validate its performance in real industrial environments.

Regarding CS2, the gear-motor factory achieved an impressive 86% reduction in global lead time (KPI2.1), leading to faster order fulfillment and improved responsiveness. Additionally, the global output (KPI2.3) increased by approximately nine gear motors, enhancing overall production capacity without requiring additional resources, as the global capacity (KPI2.4) remained unchanged at 0% growth. Simulations further revealed a 33% reduction in production time (KPI2.5) and a 50% decrease in production area (KPI2.6), optimizing workflow efficiency and space utilization. While these advancements indicate substantial productivity gains, the global productivity increase (KPI2.2) and the effectiveness of automatic scheduling (KPI2.7) remain under investigation, requiring further research and validation.

In CS3, the manufacturer in the polymer sector achieved the successful development and implementation of a new production module (KPI3.3), i.e., a new KH, which can be utilized by car manufacturers. This advancement demonstrates the company’s

commitment to innovation and its ability to meet industry demands with enhanced manufacturing capabilities. While this milestone marks a significant achievement, ongoing research is being conducted to assess the impact on the OEE (KPI3.1) and the NVAA (KPI3.2). These KPIs remain under investigation, aiming to further optimize operational efficiency and streamline production processes.

Regarding CS4, the car manufacturer showcases significant improvements in production efficiency through the integration of optimization and simulation in the KRS. The system's reprogramming time (KPI4.1) was fully optimized, achieving a 100% improvement, allowing for faster adaptation to production changes. Additionally, the KH preparation time (KPI4.2) was reduced by 21%, streamlining material handling and assembly processes. Impressively, the total reconfiguration time of the KRS has been reduced to 26% through the simulation of different KRS configuration setups. However, ongoing research is being conducted to evaluate the impact on OEE (KPI4.4), the reduction in disruptions (KPI4.3) and the decrease in NVAA (KPI4.5) to further refine operational efficiency.

6.3 Limitations and future research

On the technical aspects of our approach, the absence of an OPC UA infrastructure presents a significant challenge in integrating DTs with production modules. Without this standardized communication protocol, manufacturers must either invest in establishing an OPC UA infrastructure or develop custom APIs to bridge the gap between production equipment and DTs. Both options come with additional costs, implementation complexity, and potential delays. Developing APIs for legacy machines and production systems often requires extensive reverse engineering, especially when dealing with proprietary protocols or limited documentation. This lack of seamless connectivity hinders real-time data exchange, reducing the effectiveness of DTs in enabling predictive maintenance, process optimization, and intelligent automation. Consequently, organizations without an existing OPC UA setup face a substantial barrier to efficient DT deployment, requiring additional resources to ensure interoperability and real-time data synchronization.

On the business aspects, the complexity of DT configuration adds another layer of difficulty, as it cannot be handled solely by production experts. While production specialists understand the operational requirements, configuring DTs requires expertise in data engineering and IT infrastructure, particularly for managing data sources, structuring information models, and ensuring compatibility with existing enterprise systems. Legacy production systems, often built on outdated technologies with limited connectivity options, further complicate this process. The need for system modernization or API development to integrate these legacy systems with DTs demands additional investment and technical expertise. These limitations make adopting DTs particularly challenging for digitally immature or traditional manufacturing organizations, which may lack the necessary infrastructure, expertise, and resources. Without significant digital transformation efforts, such companies struggle to implement DTs effectively, limiting their ability to leverage Industry 4.0 innovations for competitive advantage.

The evaluation results presented in Section 6.2, along with the identified limitations, highlight key areas for future research and development. A primary direction involves conducting further investigations to assess the impact of our approach on KPIs that remain under evaluation. This necessitates the research, development and deployment of additional DTs tailored for each distinct production environment, integrating relevant functionalities such as simulation and optimization techniques designed to address case-specific challenges.

Furthermore, addressing the business limitations and the inherent challenges in configuring and deploying DTs, the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) presents a promising avenue for facilitating the automated generation of DT models. In particular, LLMs could streamline the creation of standardized DTs, such as AAS-based, by generating structured DT representations based on predefined templates and ontologies [63, 64]. Indeed, the combination of LLMs with manufacturing domain ontologies could enable the automatic mapping of data sources to DT model attributes, leading to more efficient, scalable, and customizable DT implementations. This synergy between LLMs and semantic knowledge representation holds significant potential for overcoming the complexities of DT adoption and standardization in industrial settings [65, 66].

7 Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive approach to integrating DTs and smart services within RMSs to enhance modularity, flexibility, and efficiency in industrial environments. Through the analysis of four industrial case studies, the research identifies business and user requirements, derives KPIs, and proposes a conceptual architecture that enables reconfigurable and data-driven manufacturing. The study introduces the “Module” concept, combining a production module with its DT, providing a structured framework for modularity, self-awareness, predictive maintenance and real-time simulation and optimization.

The findings indicate that most KPIs were successfully achieved or even exceeded, showcasing the significant impact of DT-enabled manufacturing on production efficiency and flexibility. Key advancements include substantial reductions in lead time, production time, and operational costs, along with improved decision-making through predictive maintenance, simulation, and optimization. Additionally, the study highlights several technical and business challenges, such as the complexity of DT configuration, integration with legacy systems, and the need for standardized interoperability frameworks.

Future research should focus on the further evaluation of the proposed architecture, while also on exploring Large Language Models (LLMs) for automated DT generation, AI-driven decision-making, and cross-company collaboration in modular production. This research contributes to the ongoing digital transformation of manufacturing, paving the way for scalable, intelligent, and adaptive production ecosystems that can respond dynamically to market demands.

Compliance with ethical standards

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. In addition, this research did not involve human participants or animals as the subject of study.

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